

Supplementary Materials S1: Protocol Details

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Notes for readers. This document supplements the manuscript titled “*Recent Advancements in Course Recommendation Systems in the Era of Large Language Models (2022–2025)*”. It provides protocol details referenced in the Methods section (information sources, exact search strings, screening workflow, and the data-extraction template). The manuscript follows PRISMA 2020 as reporting guidance; the formal PRISMA citation appears in the main paper.

S1. Review Protocol (Full Details)

S1.1 Information Sources and Timeframe

Databases: ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink/Open, ERIC. arXiv used for background only (preprints not synthesized as core evidence).

Eligibility window for core synthesis: 1 January 2022–31 December 2025.

Run dates: Database searches were executed on 25–27 August 2025. During revision, we performed a final update sweep on **5–7 January 2026** (backward/forward citation chasing and manual updates), while keeping eligibility restricted to 2022–2025.

S1.2 Exact Search Strings and Run Dates

Source	Run date	Exact query string
ACM DL	25 August 2025	("course recommendation" OR "MOOC recommendation" OR "session-based recommendation") AND (transformer OR "knowledge graph" OR sequence OR LLM OR RAG) AND ("cold-start" OR fairness OR re-ranking)
IEEE Xplore	25 August 2025	((("course recommendation") OR ("MOOC") OR ("session-based recommendation"))) AND (transformer OR "knowledge graph" OR sequence OR LLM OR RAG) AND ("cold-start" OR fairness OR "re-ranking")

SpringerLink/Open	26 August 2025	("course recommendation" OR "MOOC recommendation") AND ("knowledge graph" OR transformer OR sequence OR LLM OR RAG) AND (fairness OR "cold-start" OR re-ranking)
ERIC	27 August 2025	(course recommendation) AND (transformer OR "knowledge graph" OR LLM OR RAG) AND (fairness OR "cold-start")

Filters applied where available: English; 2022–2025; archival peer-reviewed outlets (journals or refereed conference proceedings). ArXiv was used only for discovery/background and not counted in core synthesis.

S1.3 Deduplication and Version Handling

Duplicates were removed via manual filtering (title/DOI matching). Where a peer-reviewed version existed for a preprint, the peer-reviewed item was retained. Preprints were logged as *Background* and not counted as core synthesis evidence.

S1.4 Screening Forms

Title/abstract screen (Yes/No):

- Recommender-system study with direct relevance to *course* recommendation in educational settings (university/MOOC/corporate learning)
- Empirical evaluation is indicated (offline metrics, online study, or user study)
- English language
- Publication year within 2022–2025 (eligible window for core synthesis)

Full-text screen (Yes/No):

- Archival peer-reviewed publication (journal or refereed conference/workshop proceedings)
- A course recommendation job (or a well-defined equivalent, such course enrollment prediction used for recommendation) is presented in the paper.
- Sufficient reporting for extraction: assessment procedure and datasets are explained (e.g., split strategy and candidate set where available)
- At least one quantitative outcome is reported: recommendation metrics (e.g., HR@K, nDCG@K, Precision/Recall, AUC, MAE/RMSE) and/or fairness/feasibility measures

Version handling (applied at full-text stage):

- If both a preprint and a peer-reviewed version exist for the same study, the peer-reviewed version is retained for core synthesis.
- Preprint-only works may be cited as background but are excluded from the core synthesis set.

S1.5 PRISMA Flow (Counts—aligned to the manuscript)

The manuscript’s core synthesis set contains **21** peer-reviewed CRS studies (2022–2025), listed in Table 2 (Main Manuscript: Included peer-reviewed education recommendation studies (2022–2025) used in this review) of the main paper. Database searches were executed on 25–27 Aug 2025, and we incorporated additional eligible studies during manuscript development via citation chasing and manual updates, with a final sweep on **5–7 Jan 2026**, while keeping eligibility restricted to 2022–2025.

PRISMA flow The counts below reflect the end-to-end record accounting which are used to produce the final included set in Table 2 (Main Manuscript: Included peer-reviewed education recommendation studies (2022–2025) used in this review). To perform deduplication manual title and DOI matching are used. Because some database interfaces do not provide stable export identifiers across runs and access contexts, we report the consolidated manuscript-level counts rather than per-database export files.

Records identified from databases (ACM/IEEE/Springer/ERIC):	46
Records identified from other methods (citation chasing/manual additions):	12
Total records identified:	58
Duplicates removed:	8
Records screened (title/abstract):	50
Excluded at title/abstract:	23
Full-text articles assessed for eligibility:	27
Full-text articles excluded, with reasons:	6
Studies included in the core synthesis (peer-reviewed CRS, 2022–2025):	21

Note: Peer-reviewed background reviews and CRS-adjacent preprints/workshops are cited only for context or deployment considerations and are not counted as core CRS empirical evidence in the PRISMA synthesis set.

S1.6 Reasons for Exclusion at Full-text

Reason	Count
Not focused on CRS / out of scope	4
Conceptual/UI-only (no experiments)	1
Preprint only (excluded from core synthesis; may appear in background tables)	1

S1.7 Where the included and background lists are reported

This manuscript separates evidence tiers in the Appendix tables:

- **Core peer-reviewed CRS empirical evidence (2022–2025):** Table 2 (Included peer-reviewed education recommendation studies (2022–2025) used in this review).
- **Peer-reviewed background/context:** Table 3 (Main Manuscript: Background-peer).
- **Preprints/prototypes (background only):** Table 4 (Main Manuscript: Background-preprints).

S1.8 Data-Extraction Template

Extracted fields: Citation; Venue/Year; Task; Datasets; Methods; Baselines; Evaluation Protocol (split/candidates when available); Metrics; *Within-Paper* Deltas (baseline→best only when explicitly stated); Artifacts (code/data links); Inclusion/Exclusion notes; Limitations.

S1.9 Operational Definitions

nDCG@K, HR@K.

Exposure parity: Group-wise difference in weighted top- K exposure (as defined in the manuscript).

Domain tags: University (fixed-term curricula), MOOC (continuous enrollment), Corporate/Upskilling.

S1.10 Deviations from Protocol

No deviations affecting eligibility criteria were introduced. The **5–7 Jan 2026** sweep was an additive coverage check (citation chasing and manual verification) under the same predefined criteria and the same eligibility window (2022–2025).

S1.11 Reproducibility Artifacts

Along with the selection criteria, this supplement includes the full search queries and run dates.

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